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Effective School Health Hygiene: A Tool for Sustainable Public Health Education at Secondary School Level of Education in Nigeria

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Abstract

The paper examines the effective school health hygiene: a tool for sustainable public health education at secondary school level of education in Nigeria. Relevant literature were reviewed such as concept of health education, health education programme, components of health education programme, school health, health aspect of school, public health, school health as a strategy to improve public health education, problems associated with the school health. Therefore, the study recommends that student involvement should be encourage in the health initiatives such as forming health clubs or peer education programs, parent engagement in health education by offering workshops and resources to support healthy habit at home, to encourage regular assessments and screening for student to identify and address health issues earlier, Community partnerships in collaboration with local health care providers, public health agencies and community organizations to expand health education resources.

Keywords: School health, Public Health Education.

Introduction

Schools are essential for young people to acquire knowledge, socio emotional skills including self regulation, resilience and critical thinking skills that provide the foundation for a healthy future. Access to education, safe and supportive school environments have been linked to better health outcomes (Muhammad & Haruna, 2021). Furthermore, good health is linked to reduced drop-out rates and greater educational attainment, educational performance, employment and productivity. World Health Organisation has long recognized the link between health and education and the potential for schools to play a crucial role in safeguarding student health and well being. In 1995, WHO launched the Global School Health Initiative which aimed to strengthen approaches to health promotion in schools, among those approaches include pairing children with health services occupies an important place (World Health Organisation, 2006).

Health Education at Secondary School Level of Education

Health education refers to consciously constructed opportunities for learning involving some form of communication designed to improve health literacy including improving knowledge and developing life skills which are conducive to individual and community health (WHO, 2006). School Health Encyclopedia, (2019) sees Health education as education that consists of a planned, sequential curriculum that addresses physical, mental, emotional and social dimensions of health. Health services are provided to students to appraise, protect, and promote health. These services include the provision of emergency and primary care access and referral to community health services and management of chronic health conditions.

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A healthy school environment attends to the physical and aesthetic surroundings and to a psychosocial climate and culture that maximizes the health of students and staff. Health education is a profession of educating people about health. Areas within this profession encompass environmental health, physical health, social health, emotional health, intellectual health and spiritual health as well as sexual and reproductive health education (Donatelle, 2009). Health education can be defined as the principle by which individuals and groups of people learn to behave in a manner conducive to the promotion, maintenance, or restoration of health (UNESCO, 2018).

According to United State Joint Committee on Health Education and Promotion Terminology, (2001), Health education is any combination of planned learning experiences based on sound theories that provide individuals, groups and communities the opportunity to acquire information and the skills needed to make quality health decisions. Health education is systematic process of imparting knowledge, skills, attitude and behavior toward anticipation, recognition, evaluation and control of communicable and non communicable diseases, sanitation, pollution and all other forms of threat that may hinder well being of individual and community.

Health Education Programme at Secondary School Level of Education

Health education programme is any planned activity or set of activities aimed at increasing health literacy and developing life skills conducive to health e.g. decision making, problem solving, critical thinking, interpersonal skills and stress management coping with emotions. Health education programmes are designed to promote awareness and knowledge regarding various aspects of human health. The programme is aim to educate individuals on disease prevention, healthy lifestyles and the importance of regular health screenings, these programmes play a vital role in public health by empowering individuals to take responsibility for their own health and well being (WHO, 1998).

Components of School Health Programme at Secondary School Level of Education

Number of factors influences the physical and mental health of school children and their learning process. These factors include health conditions of the children themselves, physical and social environment in their school, quality of life of their parents, their own knowledge about health promoting practices and availability of health services around them. These factors according to UNESCO, (2010) can be achieved through the following components:

- 1. School Health Environment:** School environment plays a pivotal role in the retention and learning outcomes of students. Availability of proper facilities is a pre-requisite for creating a healthy environment in a school. Provision of following facilities contributes in creating a conducive environment for the children in the school such as Safe clean drinking water (with regular water quality monitoring), Gender and culturally appropriate sanitation/toilet facilities, adequately spacious class rooms with comfortable seating arrangements and Play grounds etc. and child friendly environment access for disabled and physically challenged.
- 2. School Health Education:** Children are at a greater risk of various infections and diseases. Schools have the responsibility to educate their students and foster among them healthy and hygienic behaviour. They need to warn their students about various health risks and guide them how to protect themselves and others against diseases and other forms of ill-health by adopting health and hygiene promoting habits and practices.
- 3. School Health Services:** Young children are prone to many diseases. In the developing countries, where health services for the general public are poor and overall knowledge about health care is low, parents and teachers are unable to detect health problem of children which impede their learning. Provision of health services to the children and young students in following forms fall under this category; Health screening (medical checkup) of students on regular basis, Referral of students with health problems to medical centres for treatment or rehabilitation, De-worming campaigns among others.
- 4. School Nutrition Programmes:** Nutritional level affects overall health and consequently the pace of learning among the children. Nutritional inputs can increase both attendance and quality of education. Provision of following inputs to schools can be grouped under nutrition component of school health programme such as. Good supplements for malnourished children, Food as incentive to enhance enrolment and attendance, Promotion of use of iodized salt School feeding or school lunch programme for all students in schools.

School Health Hygiene at Secondary School Level of Education

School health is the comprehensive efforts of developing, implementing and evaluating services both within the school and the community that provide each and every student with the resources needed to thrive within a healthful environment, (American school health association, 2023). School Health can also be describe as a process of enhancing the health attitude and practices in school which may be applicable to maintain physical, mental and social well being in the community.

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Health Aspect at Secondary School Level of Education

It is widely recognized that schools can play an important role in promoting society's health. Much effort has been invested over recent years in health education techniques for schools in low income communities including child to child methods, curriculum development and the productions of locally appropriate education materials. However, the impact of the actual fabric and management of school premises on child health has been relatively neglected. Many schools fail to provide healthy environments for their pupils. Poorly designed and maintained schools can be a source of disease and ill health. Sick children also make poor learners. It is therefore, the concept tempting to suggest that all these problems are the products of poverty and that the answer is to improved socio economic status of one's nation (Abraham, et al, 2005).

Public Health at Secondary School Level of Education

Is the science and art of preventing disease, prolonging life and promoting health through the organized efforts and informed choices of society, organizations, public, private, communities and individuals (Gatseva & Argirova, 2011). To Abraham, et al, (2005) Public health also refers to the aggregate at which health is been maintain in the community that include sanitation, structural safety, nuisance prevention, water supply and quality, pollution, pest and insect control, open defecation management, waste management and improve indoor air quality among others.

School Health for Sustainable Public Health Education at Secondary School Level of Education

It must be stressed that, there is no simple technical strategy for achieving and improving a healthy school community or environment; hence there is need to synchronize or practice the following strategy in Nigeria as mentioned by Abraham et al, (2005).

- 1. Commitment and Motivation:** There is no doubt that, the single and most important factor in achieving a healthy school environment is the presence of committed and informed people. The emphasis should be on the commitment as there are plenty of evidence that shows the information is not enough, People are often well aware of the health risks and the theories of contamination but do not act on that knowledge. People who are not committed will always find reasons for not acting while a committed person will seek ways around apparently insuperable problems, if necessary committed people will also seek out information. There is no simple formula for making people committed. However, recognizing and valuing people's efforts and ensuring that there is sufficient scope for their own decision making and creativity can go a long way towards encouraging sustained commitment. The essence of commitment is a person's belief that his or her efforts can make a difference.
- 2. Free Environment:** Evidently, faeces on the ground will be a threat to health. The point to be made though is that of staff, pupils, parents and governing bodies of schools should consider the whole school environment not just classrooms but ideally concern should extend to the streets and fields between home and school include the school compound. Success in eliminating material from a school compound is dependent on informed and responsible pupils, supervision of young children that may defecate around, compound fence, and vigilance to stop animals and outsiders from defecating in the compound rather going toilets which are conveniently located, reliable, clean, reasonably odour free and reasonably private.
- 3. Safe Drinking Water:** The condition required for clean water is well known but often they are unachievable. Recommendations to boil all water are of little value in a society where fuel is expensive and scarce. Advice about deep boreholes is of no use to a resource starved school. Rather than concentrating on the source of the water, achievable measures are often those concerned with the handling of available water. Frequently, water from a tap or pump is reasonably clean, but has become contaminated by the time it reaches someone's mouth. For example, if people are dipping their hands into a water container to scoop up water in a cup, it may likely contaminating it with germs from their hands. Similarly, in some circumstances covering the water container with a lid may be an important step.
- 4. Convenient Hand Washing Arrangements:** In many countries awareness is widespread of the importance of washing one's hands after defecation. It is reasonable to suppose that it is one of the central planks of all school health education programmes. However, it is equally clear that hand washing is a practice that is widely ignored. Spreading the message of the importance of hand washing is not enough and it must also be an easy and convenient thing to do. People will not normally go out of their way to wash their hands if the tap or water source is distant from the toilet, people are unlikely to use it if water is stored in a relatively high sided tank and it may be difficult for younger children to use. Similarly, wells with high sides may discourage people from drawing water. Taps or water tanks which are constantly surrounded by mud may be discouraging. Hand pumps may be too stiff for a small child to use or it may be difficult to pump and wash one's hands at the same time.

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- 5. Structural Safety:** It is obvious that, the health of children will not be enhanced if the school building falls down. This is more the concern of engineers and builders, but teaching staff should check their school rooms on occasional basis for cracks in the main structure of more immediate importance are small scale structural issues or problems like doors falling off their hinges, rotten floor boards, broken glass, exposed nails and broken paving stones. While large scale structural problems are likely to require significant amounts of money to solve, a simple but systematic safety audit can reveal hazards which have simple remedies in many societies, communal work sessions are traditional. If parents can be persuaded to work together even just for one day once a year then such a labour force will inevitably include people with specialist skills can tackle much of the heavier structural repair work. Working together, parents can accomplish tasks such as clearing away broken concrete, rebuilding eroded steps, replacing rotten fence posts, relaying roofing sheets and repairing furniture and play equipment etc.
- 6. Adequate Cleaning and Maintenance:** Problems of structural safety can often be avoided through careful routine maintenance. Dealing with broken roof tiles or undermined foundations straightaway as soon as they occur, minimizes the need for expensive structural repairs later. Often, where a capital budget is available for construction but resources for routine upkeep inadequate, the result is dilapidated buildings which need to be replaced far earlier than should be necessary. The key to good maintenance is not letting the situation deteriorate too far before taking action. Broken, clogged or soiled toilets in particular will deteriorate rapidly if action is not taken immediately.

Problems Associated with School Health at Secondary School Level of Education

There are many problems associated with the school health and these problems can hinder well being of school children, staffers and parent as well as individuals members in the community as cited by Abraham et al, (2005) and include the following;

- 1. Location of the School:** In many cases the most dangerous aspect of a school is its location, when informal urban settlements grow up, the best land is generally taken at the outset for residential houses. Schools are often built on the least desirable land for example, on the site of an old waste dump or in areas prone to flooding or subsidence. Schools are also often located on busy roads increasing the risk of accidents or at some distance from the community they are intended to serve.
- 2. Indoor Air Quality:** There is a wide range of potential indoor air pollutants which may influence the health of school children. Pollution from heating stoves can lead to chronic respiratory diseases and carcinomas. In a crowded environment, airborne bacteria and viruses can cause cross infection. Other threats include rotten matter produced by moulds and fungal growths, fine dust, gaseous and particulate compounds from building materials and radon gas. Many health problems are associated with these pollutants including acute respiratory infections and asthma.
- 3. Noise:** High levels of noise can cause irritation, encourage aggressiveness, reduce physical and mental performance, and cause discomfort and headaches. Exceedingly loud and continual noise can lead to more serious problems. Children with hearing problems, visually impaired children, and children with learning difficulties are particularly dependent on a good acoustic environment.
- 4. Sanitation:** Without sufficient clean and functioning toilets children will defecate in and around the school compound. In such situations the school and its surroundings are likely to become infested with parasite. Neglected school compounds tend to accumulate waste both from within the school itself and dumped by people from outside. When waste builds up because of a municipal strike for example, school grounds are likely to become a natural dumping site since they probably represent one of the few accessible open spaces. If the case was left unquiet, school buildings adjacent to health buildings, medical waste including items such as used syringes can frequently be found on the ground which may be very harmful and of a greater risk to health.
- 5. Water Supply:** Many of the oral infections can also spread via contaminated drinking water, Children dipping or putting their unwashed hands into a shared drinking water supply is a typical route of contamination. But problems can also arise from water which is not used for drinking, if rain water or flood water is allowed to stand in puddles or drainages the breeding of mosquitoes and other insects may be encouraged and leading to transmission of diseases such as malaria, dengue fever and schistosomiasis. Similar problems can arise from accumulated waste which additionally may attract flies, rodents and dogs.

Conclusion

School health and public health education is not only limited to the dissemination of health related information but rather also fostering the motivation, skills and confidence (self-efficacy) necessary to take action to improve health as well as the

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communication of information concerning the underlying social, economic and environmental conditions impacting on health as well as individual risk factors and risk behaviors and use of the health care system. The main purpose of school health and public health education therefore is not only to increase knowledge about personal health behaviors but also to develop skills that demonstrate the political feasibility and organizational possibilities of various forms of action to address social, economic and environmental determinants of health.

Recommendations

The following are the recommendations outline by the writers;

- i. Students involvement should be encourage in the health initiatives such as forming health clubs or peer education programs.
- ii. Parent's engagement in health education by offering workshops and resources to support healthy habit at home.
- iii. To encourage regular assessments and screening for student to identify and address health issues earlier.
- iv. Community partnerships in collaboration with local health care providers, public health agencies and community organizations to expand health education resources.
- v. Public health advocacy toward maintaining a healthy community.
- vi. Enlightenment on how to make safe drinking water through purification methods.
- vii. Free environment should be encourages through provision of modern toilet facilities.
- viii. Avoidances of any form of pollution (air, water, sand and noise) among others that may result to unhealthy community.
- ix. Hand washing environment and facilities should also be provided so as to prevent contamination and spread of disease from and among members of the community.
- x. Environmental cleaning and maintenance habit as well as removal of all nuisances in the school premises and in the community.

References

- Abraham, A., Henock,A., Dejene, H., Takele, T., &Wossen, T. (2005). *Ethiopia public health training initiative*, debub university ethiopia,the carter center.
- American school health association, (2023). Retrieved on 24 February 2023 from <https://www.ashaweb.org/what-is-school-health/>.
- Donatelle, R. (2009). *Promoting healthy behavior change*. Health the basics. (pp. 4). 8th edition. San francisco, ca: pearson education, inc.
- Gatseva, P. D. Argirova, M. (2011). *Public health: the science of promoting health*. *Journal of public health*. 19 (3):205–206.
- Joint Committee on Terminology, (2001). Report of the 2000 joint committee on health education and promotion terminology. *American journal of health education*. 32 (2): 89–103. School Health Encyclopedia, (2019). Retrieved on 10 December 2023 from www.encyclopedia.com.
- Muhammad, A.S. & Haruna, A.S. (2021). Satisfaction with Life among Nursing Students in Northern Nigeria: Implications for Counselling. *Zamfara International Journal of Education* 1(1), 398-410.
- UNESCO, (2010). School Health Program, a strategic approach for improving health and education in Pakistan. Retrieved from <https://healtheducationresources.unesco.org>.
- UNESCO, (2018). International technical guidance on sexuality education: an evidence- informed approach (pdf). Paris: p. 82.
- World Health Organization, (1998). List of basic terms. Health promotion glossary. (pp. 4). Retrieved on 25 March, 2023, https://www.who.int/hpr/nphj/dooocs/hp_glossary_en.pdf.
- World Health Organization. (2006). Constitution of the world health organization – basic documents, forty-fifth edition, supplement, October 2006.